

COcyber Strengthens Ties Between Europe's Civilian and Defence Cybersecurity Sectors

Brussels, Belgium – Europe faces numerous cybersecurity challenges, including global threats, attacks on critical infrastructure, and a fragmented landscape lacking sufficient collaboration. **With a budget of 2.97M€ co-funded by the European Union, the [COcyber](#) project emerges as a timely response to address these pressing issues.**

Over the next two years, **the project will facilitate the exchange of knowledge, best practices, and information between the civilian and defence cybersecurity spheres.** Led by **EIT Digital**, a multidisciplinary team of five European organisations will develop online tools, frameworks, activities, and policy recommendations to align actions within the European Union.

Public Consultations: A Participatory Approach to Collaboration

To kick off its activities, COcyber is now conducting the first round of public consultations, focusing on **assessing the need to foster collaboration between the cybersecurity civilian and defence sectors.** Using methods such as questionnaires and focus groups, **the project will gather input from key stakeholders in cybersecurity, defence, and diplomacy.** Feedback gathered notably from high-level experts at the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA), European Defence Agency (EDA), and the European Commission will guide these consultations, with discussions involving national ministries, SMEs, and start-ups to address critical collaboration issues.

As a part of the initial needs assessment, **an [online survey](#) is now open, and professionals dealing with cybersecurity topics are invited to contribute their insights** on why and how we should strengthen collaboration between the civilian and defence cybersecurity sectors in Europe.

**Cybersecurity Professionals,
we want to hear from you!**

Fill in our **survey** and help enhance **collaboration** across public and private sectors in **defence and cybersecurity**.

cocyber.eu/cocyber-survey

Building Trustworthy Cybersecurity Infrastructures through the COcyber Platform

With the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) [Threat Landscape 2024](#) highlighting a surge in cybersecurity attacks amid ongoing geopolitical conflicts – setting new records in both frequency and impact, COcyber stands out by offering a **first-of-its-kind platform** that bridges the gap between the civilian and defence cybersecurity sectors in Europe.

COcyber has recently launched the first version of a **trusted and participatory information-sharing platform** at cocyber.eu. It will be continuously updated with resources, articles, and other relevant information, serving as a channel for knowledge exchange and driving innovation and research synergies in cybersecurity.

COcyber will also organise high-impact activities and events, bringing together both sectors to focus on **cybersecurity, innovation, technologies that could serve both civilian and defence purposes (dual-use), governance, and stakeholder engagement**. At the policy level, the project's outcomes will co-define **policy recommendations** to harmonise actions at both the Member State and European levels.

Joining Forces for a Resilient Cybersecurity Ecosystem

The COcyber project engages a **broad spectrum of stakeholders** critical to the cybersecurity ecosystem, including **Government and Regulatory Bodies, Private Sector, Academia and Research Institutions, International and Defence Organizations, and Civil Society and End Users**. As part of the civilian and defence spheres, cybersecurity firms and SMEs alike benefit from COcyber's platform for collaboration, knowledge

exchange, and engagement with decision-makers. This provides both groups with networking opportunities, access to cutting-edge solutions and resources, and valuable insights that will help them shape and influence the cybersecurity landscape.

COcyber brings together partners with a shared **commitment to European cybersecurity resilience**: [EIT Digital](#), [European Organisation for Security](#), [The Lisbon Council for Economic Competitiveness](#), [Université Libre de Bruxelles](#) and [AUSTRALO](#) These organisations will lead the development, outreach, and policy activities that will drive the project's success.

Members of the COcyber Team gathered in Brussels @COcyber project

Follow COcyber on [LinkedIn](#) and [Bluesky](#) - stay tuned for further developments in this collaborative ecosystem!

For more information, **get in touch with us at contact@cocyber.eu**.

Disclaimer

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